

Participant Informed Consent Form

**PHARMACOKINETICS OF DRUGS USED TO TREAT DRUG SENSITIVE-TUBERCULOSIS IN
BREASTFEEDING MOTHER-INFANT PAIRS:**

AN OBSERVATIONAL PHARMACOKINETIC STUDY

List of investigators and co-investigators:

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Introduction

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Ask us if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen because you are taking medication for TB and are currently pregnant or breastfeeding your baby.

What is the purpose of the study?

When a woman takes medicine during breastfeeding, a small amount usually passes through the breastmilk to the infant. For the drugs used to treat TB, there is very little information about how much of the medicine reaches the infant. It is important to know this, because the amount might be enough to offer the baby some protection against TB.

Do I have to take part?

It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you do decide to take part you will be given this information sheet to keep and be asked to sign a consent form. You will still be free to withdraw at any time and without giving a reason. This will not affect the standard of care you receive. If you do decide to withdraw at a later stage, your samples will be removed and destroyed.

What will happen to me if I take part?

You will be given sufficient time to consider whether you wish to participate in this study. If you are still pregnant when you decide to join the study, we will discuss how to contact you after the baby has been born. If you are already breastfeeding, we will invite you to come for sampling.

We will then invite you to attend the clinic for a full day on one occasion. We will insert a small plastic tube into a vein in your arm so that we can take several samples of a small amount of blood (1-2ml) before and at four further intervals after you have taken your medicine. We will give you your morning dose of medication with breakfast. Shortly after each blood sample we will also ask for a small sample (2-5ml) of breastmilk. In total we will take five blood samples and five breastmilk samples over the day. As we are interested to know how much drug your baby receives, we wish to take a small spot of blood from the baby on two occasions. This will be done with by pricking their heel with a very small needle.

You will be asked questions regarding your age, background, medical history, and your health experience while taking TB treatment and breastfeeding. The information will be captured on clinical research forms and study questionnaires.

After the days at the clinic, we will arrange for you to transfer back to the routine KCCA clinic, although if we have any concerns about your health or the health of your baby, we will make appropriate arrangements for your care.

The study team will be available at all times should you have any side effects or concerns about your health or about the study.

What are side effects/ risks of taking part?

During this study, we will not be changing your medicines. Placing the cannula in your arm may be associated with a small amount of discomfort or bruising. Expressing breastmilk is a straightforward process, but may be associated with some discomfort if you have not done this before; if it is causing you more than a small amount of discomfort, we will not proceed with this part of the study.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

You are not likely to benefit immediately as a result of taking part in this study. However, the information that we gain will help us fully understand the best and safest way to treat tuberculosis in mothers who are breastfeeding their babies, and this may be of benefit to you in the future.

What if new information becomes available?

Sometimes during the course of a research project, new information becomes available about the area that is being studied. If you have any concerns about it you should discuss this with your doctor. Any preliminary findings from our research will be communicated to the KCCA clinics

What happens when the research study stops?

After the study period ends, your clinical care will continue via the same clinic as where your TB treatment has been taking place. We will follow the clinic record to see that you completed your TB treatment.

Handling blood Samples

The samples will be kept in a locked freezer in the Infectious Diseases Institute. ALL THESE SAMPLES WILL BE CODED ANONYMOUSLY (but will be linked to details that we will collect about your drug levels or treatment response). We will keep your sample until the study is complete. The samples will be considered to be a gift to the IDI, which will act as a custodian of all the samples obtained as part of this project. It is important to remember that this will only be identified by a unique code, and your name will not be given out.

Will my taking part in this study be kept confidential?

Confidentiality will be maintained at all times. All samples will be coded (but it will be possible to link results to anonymised data collected from this study). We will combine all the results from this study and present the data on groups of patients (rather than individual patients). No individual will be identifiable from any presentation or publication that ensues from this research.

What will happen to the results of the research study?

We will combine all the results from the patients taking part in the study, and publish any results in medical journals. Results will be communicated with the KCCA clinic, and any results which change how breastfeeding women with TB are treated will be communicated through the ATIC newsletter and **the IDI website**. No individuals will be specifically identified in any publication.

Who is organising and funding the research?

This study is funded by the Wellcome Trust.

Who has reviewed the study?

This study has been reviewed by the Infectious Diseases Institute Research Ethics Committee and the Research Ethics Committee at the University of Liverpool You may contact the chairman

of the Research Ethics Committee if you have any questions regarding your rights as a study participant at any time.

Dr David Kateete

IDI REC Chairman

Infectious Diseases Institute — IDI Mulago, College of Health Sciences, Makerere University

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Expenses

Due to the inconvenience of attending clinic from morning until afternoon, we will re-imburse for both travel expenses and for the inconvenience of being unable to engage in other duties during that day (50 000 UGX for the inconveniences associated with the study and 20 000 UGX for transport.

Out of hour's emergency contact

For further information about this study please contact:

Dr Catriona Waitt

Infectious Diseases Institute,

Makerere University College of Health Sciences, Mulago Hospital Complex, Kampala

Email: cwaitt@liv.ac.uk

Telephone (Office): 031-230-7000, Mobile: 0772-882817

Thank you for reading this. This sheet (and a copy of the consent form) should be retained by you if you decide to participate.

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

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The undersigned, hereafter known as the Study Participant promises the following:

- The information in the patient information sheet and the written informed consent form was explained to me.
• All my questions about the study, the possible risks, side effects and taking the study drug have been answered to my satisfaction.
• I agree to take part in the study under the conditions as described in the patient information sheet.
• I understand that I am free to withdraw from the study at any point, and do not need to state a reason for this.

Name of Participant (printed) or if illiterate, make a thumbprint * in the box below

Empty box for thumbprint or name.

Signature of participant

Date: ___ / ___ / ___
Day Month Year

Witness signature (if participant unable to read or write)

*If the patient is unable to read and/or write, an impartial witness should be present during the informed consent discussion. After the written informed consent form is read and explained to the participant, and after they have orally consented to their participation in the study, and have either signed the consent form or provided their fingerprint, the witness should sign and personally date the consent form. By signing the consent form, the witness attests that the information in the consent form and any other written information was accurately explained to, and apparently understood by, the patient and that informed consent was freely given by the patient.

Name of Person Witnessing Consent (printed)

Signature of Witness

Date: ___ / ___ / ___

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Name of Person Administering Consent (printed)

Position/Title

Signature of Person Administering Consent

Date: ____ / ____ / ____
Day Month Year

Ekiwandiiko ky'omwetabi eky'okukkiriza okwetaba mu kunoonyereza.

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Omunoonyereza Omukulu

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Ennyanjula

Oyitiddwa okwetaba mu kunoonyereza. Nga tonnasalawo, kikulu okumanya lwaki okunoonyereza kukolebwa na biki ebinaakuberamu. Tukasaba oweeyo akadde osome obubaka buno n'obwegendereza era obukubaganyeeke ebirowoozo n'abantu abalala bw'oba oyagala. Tubuize bwe waba waliwo ekintu kyonna ekitategeerekeka bulungi oba nga waliwo obubaka obulala bwe wandiyagadde. Twala akadde okusalawo oba oyagala okwetabamu oba nedda.

Lwaki nnondeddwa?

Olondeddwa kubanga ofuna obujjanjabi bw'akafuba ate nga mu kiseera kino oli lubuto oba oyonsa omwana wo

Okunoonyereza kulina kigendererwa ki?

Singa omukyala akozesa eddagala ng'ayonsa, erimu ku lyo mu bipimo bitono ebiseera ebisinga liyita mu mabeere ne lituuka ku mwana. Ku ddagala erikozesebwa okujjanjaba akafuba, waliwo obubaka butono nnyo ku bungi ki obw'eddagala obutuuka ku mwana. Kikulu okumanya kino, kubanga obungi obwo bukyayinza okuwa omwana obukuumi obumala n'atafuna kafuba.

Nteekeddwa okwetabamu?

Kiri gy'oli okusalawo okwetabamu oba nedda. Singa osalawo okwetabamu ojja kuweebwa koopi y;olupapula luno olutereke era tukusabe okuteeka omukono ku fomu eraga nti okkirizza. Era ojja kuba wa ddembe okuvaamu akadde konna awatali kuwa nsonga. Kino tekijja kukosa bujjanjabi bw'ofuna bulijjo. Singa osalawo okuvaamu gye bujja eyo, ebinaakuggibwako bijja kugibwa mu tterekero era bisaanyizibwewo.

Kiki ekinaantuukako singa nneetabamu?

Ojja kuweebwa obudde obumala okwerowooza n'okusalawo okwetaba mu kunoonyereza kuno. Mu kiseera w'onaasalirawo okwetaba mu kunoonyereza kuno singa oba okyali lubuto, tujja kukubaganya ebirowoozo ku ngeri y'okukutuukirira ng'omwana azaaliddwa . Bw'oba nga mu kiseera kino oyonsa, tujja kukuyita oggibweeko omusaayi n'amabeere.

Era tujja kukuyita ku kalwaliro okumala olunaku lulamba olumu. Tujja kuyingiza mu musuwa gw'omukono gwo akapiira akatono aka pulasitiika kino kitusobozese okukujjako omusaayi ogw'enjawulo oguwera ml emu oba bbiri nga tonnamira ddagala ate ne mu biseera eby'enjawulo ng'omaze okumira eddagala. Tujja kukuwa eddagala lyo ery'okumakya wamu n'ekyenkye. Buli luvannyuma lw'okuggibwako omusaayi, tujja kukusaba amabeere matono nga gaweza mls 2-5. Omugatte tujja kukujjako omusaayi emirundi etaano era n'amabeere bwe kityo mu lunaku olwo. Olw'okuba twagala okumanya bungi ki obw'eddagala omwana wo ly'afunira mu mabeere, twandyagadde okujja akasaayi katono ku mwana emirundi ebiri. Kino kijja kukolebwa nga tufumita akayiso akatono ennyo ku kakongovvule.

Ojja kubuuzibwa ebibuuzo ebifa ku bulamu bwo, ebyafaayo byo eby'eddagala, n'obulamu bwo ng'okozesa eddagala okujjanjaba akafuba ate ng'oyonsa. Obubaka bujja kuteekebwa ku lupapula lw'eddwaliro olw'okunoonyereza n'ebibuuzo ebifa ku kunoonyereza.

Oluvannyuma lw'ennaku ku kalwaliro, tujja kukukolera entegeka okuddayo ku kalwaliro gy'ofuna eddagala eriweeza ku kawuka ka mukenenya, newandibadde singa tuba n'okutya kwonna ku mbeera y'obulamu bwo oba obw'omwana wo, tujja kukukolera entegeka ezisaanidde olabirirwe.

Ekibinja ekiri ku kunoonyereza kijja kubeerawo buli kiseera singa oba n'engeri gy'okoseddwa oba okutya ku lw'obulamu bwo oba okufa ku kunoonyereza.

Okwetabamu kulimu buzibu ki/katyabaga ki?

Mu kunoonyereza kuno, tetujja kukyusa ddagala lyo. Okuteeka akapiira mu mukono gwo kiyinza okuvaako obutawulira bulungi kutono oba okuzimba. Okujjako amabeere kukolebwa mu bulambulukufu, naye kiyinza okwekuusa ku butawulira bulungi singa kino oba tokikolangako; singa kino kikuleetera obutawulira bulungi nga bungi, tetujja kugenda mu maaso na katundu kano ak'okunoonyereza.

Okwetabamu kirimu miganyulo ki?

Oyinza obutaganyulwa mangu ddala singa weetaba mu kunoonyereza kuno. Naye, obubaka bwe tunaafuna bujja kutuyamba okutegeera mu bujuvu engeri esinga obulungi era eteriimu buzibu ey'okujjanjaba akafuba mu ba maama abayonsa abaana baabwe, era kino kikyayinza okukuganyula gye bujja.

Watya singa obubaka obupya bulabika?

Ebiseera ebimu mu kunoonyereza, obubaka obupya bulabika mu kisaawe ekinoonyerezebwako. Kino bw'oba okyekengeramu, osaana okikubaganyeeke ebirowoozo n'omusawo wo. Bye tunaasooka okuzuula mu kunoonyereza kuno bijja kutegeezebwa amalwaliro ga KCCA

Kiki ekinaabaawo singa okunoonyereza kukoma?

Ouvannyuma lw'okukomekerezera okunoonyereza, obujjanjabi bwo ku kalwaliro kujja kugenda mu maaso nga buyitira ku kalwaliro ke kamu w'ofunira obujjanjabi bw'akafuba. Tujja kugoberera ebiwandiiko byo ku kalwaliro okulaba oba wamalayo obujjanjabi bwo obw'akafuba.

Enkuuma y'omusaayi ogunaggibwa ku bantu

Ebinaggibwa ku beetabyeemu bijja kuterekebwa mu firigi esibwako kkufulu ku kitongole kya Infectious Diseases Institute. BINO BYONNA BIJJA KUWEEBWA ENNAMBA NGA TEBIRIICO MANNYA (naye bijja kukwanaganyizibwa n'ebijjuvu ebinaakunganyizibwa okuva ku bungi bw'eddagala lyo oba engeri gy'oyisibwamu eddagala lino). Tujja kutereka ebinaakuggibwako okutuusa ng'okunoonyereza kuwedde. Ebinaakuggibwako bijja kutwalibwa ng'ekirabo eri ekitongole ki IDI, ekijja okukola ogw'okubikuuma ng'ekitundu ku polojekiti eno. Kikulu okujjukira bino bijja kumanyibwa nga tukozeza nnamba ey'enjawulo, era erinnya lyo terijja kulagibwa wantu wonna.

Okwetaba mu kunoonyereza kuno kunaakuumibwa nga kwa kyama?

Ebyama bijja kuumibwa buli kiseera. Ebinaggibwa ku bantu byonna bijja kuweebwa ennamba (naye kijja kusoboka okubikwanaganya n'ebinaava mu kunoonyereza ebitaabeeko mannya mu kunoonyereza kuno). Tujja kugatta wamu byonna ebinaava mu kunoonyereza era tulage obubaka eri ebibinja by'abalwadde (so si buli mulwadde kinnoomu). Tewali muntu ajaa kutegeerekeka okuva mu kulaga ebinaava mu kunoonyereza kuno oba okubikuba mu kyapa nga biva mu kunoonyereza kuno.

Kiki ekinaatuuka ku binaava mu kunoonyereza kuno?

Tujja kugatta byonna ebinaava mu kunoonyereza ku balwadde abeetabyemu, era tufulumye ebinaavaamu mu butabo bw'ekisawo. Ebinaavaamu bijja kutegeezebwa amalwaliro ga KCCA, ate ebinaava mu kunoonyereza nga bikyusa engeri abakyala abayonsa nga balina akafuba gye bajjanjabwa bijja kutegeezebwanga tuyita mu mawulire agayitibwa ATIC wamu n'ekibanja kya IDI. Tewali bantu bajja kutegeerekeka butereevu mu biwandiiko byonna ebinaasaasaanyizibwa.

Ani ategese era avujjirira okunoonyereza?

Okunoonyereza kuno kuvujjiriddwa Wellcome Trust.

Ani yeekenneenyezza okunoonyereza kuno?

Okunoonyereza kuno kwekenneenyezeddwa akakiiko k'empisa mu kunoonyereza ak'ekitongole ki Infectious Diseases wamu n'akakiiko k'empisa mu kunoonyereza aka Ssettendekero wa Liverpool. Oyinza okutuukirira Ssentebe w'akakiiko k'empisa mu kunoonyereza bw'oba n'ekibuuzo kyonna ekikwata ku ddembe lyo ng'eyeetabye mu kunoonyereza kuno akadde konna.

Dr David Kateete

Ssentebe wa IDI REC

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Essimu (eya wofiisi): 0414-307-291 Ey'omungalo: +256-704-879922

Ensaasaanya

Olw'okutaataaganyizibwa ng'ojja ku kalwaliro n'omala olunaku lulamba, tujja kukuddiza ensimbi z'entambula n'okutaataaganyizibwa ate n'obutasobola kukola mirimu gyo ku olwo era tujja kukuwa ssente za Uganda 50 000/- olw'okutaataaganyizibwa nga kwekuusa ku kunoonyereza), n'e 20 000/- ku ntambula.

Okututuukirira mu biseera ebitali bya kukola nga tekyewalika

Okufuna obubaka obusingawo ku kunoonyereza kuno tukusaba otuukirire:

Dr Catriona Waitt

Infectious Diseases Institute,

Makerere University College of Health Sciences, Mulago Hospital Complex, Kampala Email:

cwaitt@liv.ac.uk

Essimu (Wofiisi): 0414-307-291, Ey'omungalo 0772-882817

Weebale nnyo okusoma bino. Koopi y'olupapula luno olulaga okukkiriza gisigaze singa osalawo okwetaba mu kunoonyereza kuno.

FOOMU ERAGA NTI OMUNTU AKKIRIZZA NG'ATEGEDDE

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Atadde omukono kuno, nga kati amanyiddwa ng'eyeetabye mu kunoonyereza asuubiza bino:

- Obubaka obuli mu lupapula lw'abalwadde wamu ne foomu eraga okukkiriza binnyinyonyoddwa.
- Ebibuuzo byange byonna ebifa ku kunoonyereza kuno, ebizibu ebizibwa okubaamu, okukosebwa n'okukozesa eddagala eriri mu kunoonyerezebwo babinzizeemu era mmatidde.
- Nzikirizza okwetaba mu kunoonyereza ku bukwakkulizo obulagiddwa mu lupapula okuli obubaka.
- Nkimanyi nti ndi a ddembe okuva mu kunoonyereza kuno akadde konna awatali kuwa nsonga reason for this.

Erinnya ly'eyetabyeemu (Mu kyapa)
gw'eyeetabyeemu oba ateeke bekinkumu mu kabokisi wammanga bw'aba tasobola
kuwandiika

Omukono

Ennaku z'omwezi: ____ / ____ / ____

Olunaku omwezi omwaka

Singa omulwadde tasobola kusoma na kuwandiika, omujulizi atalina kyekubiira atekwa okubaawo ng'okukkiriza kufunibwa n'okukubaganyizibwako ebirowoozo. Nga foomu empandiike emaze okusomerwa n'okunonyonyolwa eyeetabyeemu, era ng'ayogedde nti akkirizza okwetaba mu kunoonyereza kuno, era ng'ataddeko omukono oba ekinkumu, omujulizi atekwa okuteekako omukono era ateekeko ennaku z'omwezi ku foomu eraga okukkiriza. Mu kuteeka omukono ku foomu eno omujulizi akakasa nti obubaka obugirimu wamu n'obubaka obulala obuwandiike bwannyonyolwa bulungi era ne butegeerebwa omulwadde era nti yawaayo okukkiriza ng'ategedde bulungi era ng'akkirizza.

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Erinnya ly'omujulizi (mu kyapa)
Abaddewo mu kukkiriza

Omukono gwe

Ennaku z'omwezi: ____ / ____ / ____

Erinnya ly'awaayo okukkiriza (Mu kyapa)

Ekifo kye

Omukono gw'awaayo okukkiriza

Ennaku z'omwezi: ____ / ____ / ____

Olunaku omwezi omwaka

Participant sample storage consent form

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Reader in Clinical Pharmacology, University of
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Development Fellow
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Introduction

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Ask us if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen because you are taking medication for TB and are currently pregnant or breastfeeding your baby.

What is the purpose of the study?

When a woman takes medicine during breastfeeding, a small amount usually passes through the breastmilk to the infant. For the drugs used to treat TB, there is very little information about how much of the medicine reaches the infant. It is important to know this, because the amount might be enough to offer the baby some protection against TB.

What is the Purpose of the storage consent form? The purpose of this consent form is to give you information about storage of your samples so that you can decide whether you would want your samples to be stored for future and other related research study. If you decide that you do not want your sample to be stored, you may still participate in the study. If you agree, you will be required to sign a separate consent form for sample storage.

What will happen to your stored samples?

The study personnel will collect blood sample and breastmilk samples at your pharmacokinetic sampling visit and send this to the Infectious Diseases Institute Core laboratory. Your samples may be scored for a long time, but not longer than 10 years. The sample that is not used immediately will be stored until it is all used up in future research. The portion that is stored for future research may be shared with other scientists who carry out important work in a similar field. We will never sell your samples for profit.

What are risks of taking part?

During this study, we will not be changing your medicines. Placing the cannula in your arm may be associated with a small amount of discomfort or bruising. Expressing breastmilk is a straightforward process, but may be associated with some discomfort if you have not done this before; if it is causing you more than a small amount of discomfort, we will not proceed with this part of the study.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

You are not likely to benefit immediately as a result of taking part in this study. However, the information that we gain will help us fully understand the best and safest way to treat tuberculosis in mothers who are breastfeeding their babies, and this may be of benefit to you in the future.

Withdrawal of consent and destruction of samples.

You may withdraw this consent at any time in the study and this will not affect your participation in the study. You may request that your samples may be destroyed and no longer used in research. Any research results withdrawn prior to your withdrawal of consent will however be used.

What should you do if you have questions?

If you have questions about the storage and future use of your samples or need any more information, you should contact the study Principal Investigator. Catriona Waitt Infectious Diseases Institute, Makerere University College of Health Sciences, Mulago Hospital Complex, Kampala
Email: cwaitt@liv.ac.uk
Telephone: Mobile: 0772-882817

Thank you for reading this. This sheet (and a copy of the consent form) should be retained by you if you consent for sample storage.

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

PHARMACOKINETICS OF DRUGS USED TO TREAT DRUG SENSITIVE-TUBERCULOSIS IN BREASTFEEDING MOTHER-INFANT PAIRS:

AN OBSERVATIONAL PHARMACOKINETIC STUDY

The undersigned, hereafter known as the Study Participant promises the following:

- I have read the preceding information describing this sample collection and all questions regarding the study sample storage, and the possible risks have been answered to my satisfaction.
- I agree to take part in the study under the conditions as described in the storage consent form.
- I understand that I am free to withdraw from the study at any point, and do not need to state a reason for this.

Name of Participant (printed)
or if illiterate, make a thumbprint * in the box below

Signature of participant

Date: ____ / ____ / ____
Day Month Year

**If the patient is unable to read and/or write, an impartial witness should be present during the informed consent discussion. After the written informed consent form is read and explained to the participant, and after they have orally consented to their participation in the study, and have either signed the consent form or provided their fingerprint, the witness should sign and personally date the consent form. By signing the consent form, the witness attests that the information in the consent form and any other written information was accurately explained to, and apparently understood by, the patient and that informed consent was freely given by the patient.*

Name of Person Witnessing Consent (printed)
Witnessing Consent

Signature of Person

Date: ____ / ____ / ____

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

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Name of Person Administering Consent (printed)

Position/Title

Signature of Person Administering Consent

Date: ____ / ____ / ____
Day Month Year

Ekiwandiiko Ky'okukiriiza okutereka ebikugyibwako

PHARMACOKINETICS OF DRUGS USED TO TREAT DRUG SENSITIVE-TUBERCULOSIS IN

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Ennyanjula

Oyitiddwa okwetaba mu kunoonyereza. Nga tonnasalawo, kikulu okumanya lwaki okunoonyereza kukolebwa na biki ebinaakuberamu. Tukasaba oweeyo akadde osome obubaka buno n'obwegendereza era obukubaganyeeke ebirowoozo n'abantu abalala bw'oba oyagala. Tubuuze bwe waba waliwo ekintu kyonna ekitategeerekeka bulungi oba nga waliwo obubaka obulala bwe wandiyagadde. Twala akadde okusalawo oba oyagala okwetabamu oba nedda.

Lwaki nnondeddwa?

Olondeddwa kubanga ofuna obujjanjabi bw'akafuba ate nga mu kiseera kino oli lubuto oba oyonsa omwana wo.

Okunoonyereza kulina kigendererwa ki?

Singa omukyala akozesa eddagala ng'ayonsa, erimu ku lyo mu bipimo bitono ebiseera ebisinga liyita mu mabeere ne lituuka ku mwana. Ku ddagala erikozesebwa okujjanjaba akafuba, waliwo obubaka butono nnyo ku bungu ki obw'eddagala obutuuka ku mwana. Kikulu okumanya kino, kubanga obungi obwo bukyayinza okuwa omwana obukuumi obumala n'atafuna kafuba.

Foomu eraga okukkiriza okutereka ebinaakuggibwako erimu kigendererwa ki?

Ekigendererwa kya foomu eno kwe kukuwa obubaka obukwata ku kutereka ebimu ku binaakuggibwako kino kikuyambe okusalawo oba oyagala ebinaakuggibwako ebyo biterekebwe era bikozesebwe mu kunoonyereza gye bujja n'okulala okufaanako okwo. Singa osalawo nti toyagala binaakuggibwako kuterekebwa, okyayinza okugenda mu maaso ne weetabamu. Bw'okkiriza, kijja kukwetaagisa okuteeka omukono ku foomu ey'enjawulo etukkiriza okutereka ebinaakuggibwako.

Biki ebinaatuuka ku binaakuggibwako ne biterekebwa?

Abali ku kunoonyereza bajja kujjako omusaayi n'amabeere lw'onogenda ku kalwaliro era babiweereze ku kitongole ki Infectious Diseases Institute mu tterekero eryenkizo. Ebinaakuggibwako biyinda okuterekebwa okumala akaseera akawanvuko, naye obutasukka myaka kkumi. Ebyo ebinaaba tebikozeseddwa mangu ago bijja kuterekebwa okutuusa nga byonna bikozeseddwa mu kunoonyereza gye bujja. Ebyo ebinaaterekebwa okukozesebwa gye bujja biyinda okugabanibwa ne banna Sayansi abalala abakola omulimu omukulu mu kisaawe ekifaananako kino. Kikafuuwe ffe okutunda ebinaakuggibwako okwekolera amagoba.

Okwetabamu kulimu buzibu ki/katyabaga ki?

Mu kunoonyereza kuno, tetujja kukyusa ddagala lyo. Okuteeka akapiira mu mukono gwo kiyinza okuvaako obutawulira bulungi kutono oba okuzimba. Okujjako amabeere kukolebwa mu bulambulukufu, naye kiyinza okwekuusa ku butawulira bulungi singa kino oba tokikolangako; singa kino kikuleetera obutawulira bulungi nga bungu, tetujja kugenda mu maaso na katundu kano ak'okunoonyereza.

Okwetabamu kirimu miganyulo ki?

Oyinza obutaganyulwa mangu ddala singa weetaba mu kunoonyereza kuno. Naye, obubaka bwe tunaafuna bujja kutuyamba okutegeera mu bujuvu engeri esinga obulungi era eterimu buzibu ey'okujjanjaba akafuba mu ba maama abayonsa abaana baabwe, era kino kikyayinza okukuganyula gye bujja.

Okujjayo okukkiriza n'okusaanyaawo ebinaakuggibwako.

Oyinza okugyayo okukkiriza kuno akadde konna okuva mu kunoonyereza kuno nga kino tekijja kukosa kwetaba kwo mu kunoonyereza kuno. Oyinza okusaba ebinaakuggibwako bisaanyizibwewo era bireme kwongera kukozezebwa mu kunoonyereza. Naye ebyo ebinaava mu kunoonyereza nga tonnavaamu byo bijja kukozezebwa. singa oba n'ebibuuzo?

Bw'oba n'ebibuuzo ebifa ku kutereka n'okukozesa ebinaakuggibwako gye bujja oba nga wetaaga obubaka obulala, tuukirira omunoonyereza omukulu.

Catriona Waitt Infectious Diseases Institute, e Makerere University ku ttendekero ly'ebuyobulamu,
Mulago Hospital Complex, Kampala
Email: cwaitt@liv.ac.uk
Essimu: 0772-882817

Weebale nnyo okusoma bino. Olupapula luno lusigazeeko koopi singa okkiriza tutereke ebinaakuggibwako.

FOOMU ERAGA NTI OMUNTU AKKIRIZZA NG'ATEGEDDE

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Atadde omukono kuno, nga kati amanyiddwa ng'eyeetabye mu kunoonyereza asubiza bino:

- Nsomye obubaka obuzzeeko obunnyonnyola engeri gye bagenda okunziggyako omusaayi n'amabeere era ebibuuzo byonna ebikwata ku kutereka ebinaanzigigbwako, Okutya okuyinza okubaamu, byonna babinzizeemu ne mmatira..
- Nzikirizza okwetaba mu kunoonyereza ku bukwakkulizo obulagiddwa mu lupapula okuli obubaka.
- Nkimanyi nti ndi wa ddembe okuva mu kunoonyereza kuno akadde konna awatali kuwa nsonga reason for this.

Erinnya ly'eyetabyeemu (Mu kyapa)
gw'eyeetabyeemu oba ateeke bekinkumu mu kabokisi wammanga bw'aba tasobola kuwandiika

Omukono

Ennaku z'omwezi: ____ / ____ / ____
Ennaku omwezi omwaka

**Singa omulwadde tasobola kusoma na kuwandiika, omujulizi atalina kyekubiira ateeke okubaawo ng'okukkiriza kufunibwa n'okukubaganyizibwako ebirowoozo. Nga foomu empandiike emaze okusomerwa n'okunnyonnyolwa eyeetabyeemu, era ng'ayogedde nti akkiriza okwetaba mu kunoonyereza kuno, era ng'ataddeko omukono oba ekinkumu, omujulizi ateeke okuteekako omukono era ateekeko ennaku z'omwezi ku foomu eraga okukkiriza. Mu kuteeka omukono ku foomu eno omujulizi akakasa nti obubaka obugirimu wamu n'obubaka obulala obuwandiike bwannyonnyolwa bulungi era ne butegeerebwa omulwadde era nti yawaayo okukkiriza ng'ategedde bulungi era ng'akkirizza.*

**PHARMACOKINETICS OF DRUGS USED TO TREAT DRUG SENSITIVE-TUBERCULOSIS IN
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Erinnya ly'omujulizi (mu kyapa)
Witnessing Consent

Omukono gwe

Ennaku z'omwezi: ____ / ____ / ____

Erinnya ly'awaayo okukkiriza (Mu kyapa)

Ekifo kye

Omukono gw'awaayo okukkiriza

Ennaku z'omwezi: ____ / ____ / ____
Ennaku omwezi omwaka

Breast Milk Donor Informed consent Form

PHARMACOKINETICS OF DRUGS USED TO TREAT DRUG-SENSITIVE TUBERCULOSIS IN BREASTFEEDING MOTHER-INFANT PAIRS: AN OBSERVATIONAL PHARMACOKINETIC STUDY

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Introduction

You are being invited to contribute to the running of a research study. The Maternal and Infant Lactation pharmacokinetics (MILK) study will look at the amount of medication that transfers from a breastfeeding mother to her baby. We need to be able to measure the drugs accurately in blood, and to be able to develop the laboratory processes accurately, we need some donated samples of breast milk from mothers who are not taking any medication.

Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen because you are breastfeeding and not taking any medication.

Do I have to take part?

It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you do decide to take part you will be given this information sheet to keep and be asked to sign a consent form.

What will happen to me if I take part?

A member of the study team will give you some instructions on how to express breast milk and a clean container. We will ask you to manually express some breast milk – ideally between 10 and 30 mL and return it to the study team.

What are side effects/ risks of taking part?

Expression of breast milk is a very low risk procedure, and as you are already breastfeeding, it is usually not difficult to manually express milk. There is a small risk of bruising or discomfort.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

You are not likely to benefit immediately as a result of taking part in this study. However, the information that we gain will help us fully understand the best and safest way to treat medical conditions such as malaria or tuberculosis in mothers who are breastfeeding their babies, and this may be of benefit to you in the future.

Handling Milk Samples

The samples will be kept in a locked freezer in the Infectious Diseases Institute. ALL THESE SAMPLES WILL BE CODED ANONYMOUSLY. We will keep your sample until the study is complete. The samples will be considered to be a gift to the IDI, which will act as a custodian of all the samples obtained as part of this project. It is important to remember that this will only be identified by a unique code, and your name will not be given out.

Will my taking part in this study be kept confidential?

Confidentiality will be maintained at all times. All samples will be. We will combine all the results from this study and present the data on groups of patients (rather than individual patients). No individual will be identifiable from any presentation or publication that ensues from this research.

What will happen to the results of the research study?

We will combine all the results from the patients taking part in the study, and publish any results in medical journals. Results will be communicated with the IDI and KCCA clinics, and any results which change how breastfeeding women with conditions including malaria are treated will be communicated through the Community Advisory Board including using posters, social media channels and press releases. No individuals will be specifically identified in any publication.

Who is organising and funding the research?

This study is funded by the Wellcome Trust.

Who has reviewed the study?

This study has been reviewed by the Infectious Diseases Institute Research Ethics Committee and the Research Ethics Committee at the University of Liverpool. You may contact the chairman of the Research Ethics Committee if you have any questions regarding your rights as a donor at any time.

Dr David Kateete

IDI REC Chairman

Infectious Diseases Institute — IDI Mulago, College of Health Sciences, Makerere University

Email: david.kateete@gmail.com

Telephone (Office): 0414-307-291 Mobile: +256-704-879922

Out of hour's emergency contact

For further information about this study please contact:

Prof. Catriona Waitt

Infectious Diseases Institute,

Makerere University College of Health Sciences, Mulago Hospital Complex, Kampala

Email: cwaitt@liv.ac.uk

Telephone (Office): 031-230-7000, Mobile: 0772-882817

24-Hour Contact:

Study Coordinator: Nakijoba Ritah

Phone number: 0789314632

Thank you for reading this. This sheet (and a copy of the consent form) should be retained by you if you decide to participate.

**PHARMACOKINETICS OF DRUGS USED TO TREAT DRUG SENSITIVE
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BREASTMILK DONOR CONSENT FORM

Please initial the boxes and sign below, to confirm that:

1. The information in the patient information sheet and the written informed consent form was explained to me.
2. I am not currently taking any medication
3. I am happy to donate some breastmilk to support the development of assays

Name of Donor (printed)

Signature of donor

Date: ____ / ____ / ____

Name of Person Administering Consent (printed)

Position/Title

Signature of Person Administering Consent

Date: ____ / ____ / ____
Day Month Year

